

RECORDING OF DIFFERENT TUNES

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Abstract: In today's era of technological development, we will be able to see technological innovations and research in music education, like in all areas. As an example of this, this thesis explains the theoretical system and foundations of writing different modes.

Key words: Musical scale, musical notation, rakhahod, inversion, musical notation, Dodecaphony, harmonic.

Composers of the 20th century. We will touch on several ways of recording modern notes in the works of 20th century composers.

An example of recording atonal music (dodecaphony). Dodecaphony (Greek: twelve sounds) is a method of creating music based on the "series", a certain sequence of 12 sounds of different pitches located in the interval of one octave. A method of music composition developed by the Austrian composer Arnold Schoenberg at the beginning of the 20th century. This method is all of the octave

Based on the fact that 12 notes are of equal weight and should not be preferred over each other.

Dodecaphony is compared to traditional harmony and melody, built on the tonality and use of primary and subordinate pitches. In dodecaphonic music, all sounds are equal, and the composer can use them in any combination without following traditional harmonic rules.

Although dodecaphony faced opposition from the music community, it became an important direction in the development of modern classical music. Composers using this method strive to create new and innovative sounds while preserving the distinctive features of classical music, such as form and structure.

(Figure 1)

Professional musicians were fully aware of the crisis in music technology. The unlimited creative freedom they gained at the beginning of the 20th century led to the destruction of the foundations of the previously dominant musical language and even to sound "anarchy". At the same time, Arnold Schoenberg, the inventor of dodecaphony, became famous in the musical world for creating atonal works, and suddenly discovered that it was impossible to create completely in large musical genres. In order to create larger works from a small performance, the composer needed a certain program that would compositionally link this work together. It became clear that there is a need for a new universal and practical method of composition that any musician can perceive without losing his personality. In solving this problem, Schoenberg created the method of dodecaphony by 1923. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. The main series and its variations on the chromatic scale.
P-primary series, R-rectifier, I-inversion, RI-rectifier-inversion.

Figure 3. A. Webern. Concerto for 9 instruments op.24.

197 Mäßig (♩ = ca 60) A. Веберн. Багатели ор. 9, № 1

I. Geige 1 mit Dämpfer *pp* 2 *p* 3 *pp*

II. Geige mit Dämpfer *pp*

Bratsche am Steg mit Dpfr *pp* am Steg *pp*

Violoncell mit Dpfr *pp* *pp*

4 *p* 5 *pp* 6 *f* 7 *ff* 8 *f* 9 *pp* 10 *ppp*

rit. tempo accel. heftig. (♩ = ca 96) rit.

pizz. arco am Steg d-Saite

8 wieder mäßig (♩ = ca 60) 9 rit. 10 ♩ = ca. 44

arco pizz. arco pizz. arco

sfp *f* *p* *pp* *ppp*

sff *f* *p* *pp* *ppp*

(or microintervals) - a sound system consisting of intervals smaller than a semitone.

The names of the intervals in this system are as follows:

- $\frac{1}{3}$ — uchlik ton
- $\frac{1}{6}$ — otilik ton
- $\frac{1}{4}$ — to'rtlik ton
- $\frac{1}{8}$ — sakkizlik ton
- $\frac{1}{5}$ — beshlik ton
- $\frac{1}{12}$ — o'nikkilik ton

4-figure

Writing in a note:

0 $-\frac{3}{4}$ $-\frac{1}{2}$ $-\frac{1}{4}$ 0 $+\frac{1}{4}$ $+\frac{1}{2}$ $+\frac{3}{4}$ 0

One of the

$0 + \frac{1}{12} + \frac{2}{12} + \frac{3}{12} + \frac{4}{12} + \frac{5}{12} + \frac{6}{12} + \frac{7}{12} + \frac{8}{12} + \frac{9}{12} + \frac{10}{12} + \frac{11}{12} 32$

4-rasm

The use of various "subtle distinctions" has its place in Uzbek folk music. Neutral intervals (tertia, sexta, secunda, septima) are counted as a result of the subtle differentiation of the twelve-step tone. Jami scale recorded by V. Belyayev:

Iran based its scales and chords on a quarter-tone structure. A seventeen-step quarter-tone scale:

6-figure

Examples of microchromatics in works:

216 Lento $\text{♩} = \text{ca. } 46-48$
Э. Денисов. Фортепианное трио. ч. 1
con sord. *pp dolce espr.*
Скрипка
Виолончель *pp dolce espr.*
Lento $\text{♩} = \text{ca. } 46-48$
Фортепиано *pp dolce espr.*

215 (♩ = ca 80) В. Лютославский. Книга для оркестра. I гл. rit.

The musical score is arranged in a system of seven staves. From top to bottom, the staves are labeled: Vni I div., Vni II div., Vle div., and Vc. div. The first staff is unlabeled but contains a melodic line with dynamics *p* and *pp*. The second and third staves (Vni I and II) play a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with dynamics *p* and *pp*. The fourth and fifth staves (Vle) play a similar rhythmic pattern, with dynamics *p* and *pp*. The sixth and seventh staves (Vc) play a sustained harmonic accompaniment, with dynamics *pp*. The score includes various musical notations such as slurs, accents, and triplets. The tempo is marked as *rit.* (ritardando).

Aleatorics (Lat. playing stone) is a free text technique that allows for many performance versions.

8, 9-figure

P.Shedrin. "Poetriya"

256

Arpa I

Organo

V-ni I
div. in 2

V-ni II
div. in 2

V-le
div. in 2

V-c
div. in 4

sola

ff come sopra

sempre simile

pp

arco sul pont.

pp

pp

33

Fl. I

Fl. II

Fl. III

Fl. IV

Ob. I

Cl. I

Cl. II

Fag. I

Fag. II

Celesta

Arpa II

Organo

sempre simile

p stacc.

ff

p

ff

p

sempre simile

ff

sempre simile

ff

p

ff

p

221 a) А. Шнитке. Концерт № 2 для скрипки с орк.

Perc. I *legno*

P-no *mf*

V-no solo *ppp*

V-ni I *f*

V-ni II *f*

V-le *f*

V-c. *f*

C-b *gliss*

Кларип *mp*

18° Yuqori registrda oq va qora klavishada juda tez va erkin davriy holatda ijro

6) 41 $\text{♩} = 104$ a)

Those shown in the square are played in free tempo range.

In the 20th century, changes in music and musical phenomena, the modern composer's need to work at the boundaries of different phenomena (music, visual arts, theater), and the need to perform music in theaters led many composers to develop their own graphic music recording systems. In addition, in addition to musical notation of music, physical parameters of sound (graphs, oscillograms, etc.).

The graphic language of recording musical works can be of interest both as a graphic system of ready-made ("found") symbols, and as a space (space of musical notes) that allows creating musical images by working with elements of the language of musical staff (musical symbols). The space of a sheet of music can be compared to a geographical map, an anatomical chart, a game map, etc. Illustrative examples are taken from open sources on the Internet.

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